

MATRIX TEXTURE AND PARTICLE DISTRIBUTION
IN EXTRUDED SiC/ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Metal matrix composites containing rigid particles can be formed into different shapes by a number of standard metal working techniques. One rapid forming, high volume method is extrusion. A study was conducted in which 15 volume percent of SiC particles in 2014 aluminum alloy was extruded at various reductions of area up to 98%, and the redistribution of particles and the developed crystallographic texture were analyzed. The extrusion was carried out at 488°C in dies especially designed for high temperature extrusion. Deformation fragmented the brittle particles and tended to align them in the extrusion axis. In addition, the matrix texture became dominated by a recrystallized structure possessing a [100] preferred orientation in the direction of the extrusion axis. Presented is a discussion which describes the metal and particle flow which produced these results.

INTRODUCTION

When metal matrix composites (MMC) containing ceramic particles with l/d about unity are plastically deformed the particles are redistributed [1]. An orientation texture of metal matrix evolves even when the extrusion is performed around the recrystallization temperature of the metal, however, it has been shown that hard particles inhibit the development of texture in MMC [2,3]. The research represented in this paper correlates the degree of hot extrusion of a particulate composite, SiC/2014 aluminum with the texture in matrix and the redistribution of particles. Hot extrusion of 2014 aluminum, without the interference of non-deformable particles, produces a [111] + [100] duplex texture [4].

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

As-cast SiC/2014 aluminum containing 15 volume percent SiC was obtained from SAIC (USA) [5]. The particles were irregular but generally equiaxed with mean diameters ranging from less than $1\mu\text{m}$ to about $40\mu\text{m}$. Three inch diameter, as-cast billets were machined to one inch diameter for starting stock for extrusion. Six direct extrusion dies were designed for cross-section reduction of areas of 20%, 40%, 60%, 80%, 95% and 98%. Each die was surrounded by heating elements so that the die and the material within the die could be heated simultaneously to a temperature of about 488°C (910°F). This temperature is higher than that usually used for the extrusion of 2014 aluminum [6], however, to achieve satisfactory flow conditions a temperature near the solvus [7] is necessary. The extrusion speed was about 1.5 m/min (5 ft/min) with a water based graphite lubricant. Figure 1 shows an extrusion of a one inch billet with a reduction of cross-sectional area (RA) of 98%.

Figure 1 Extruded SiC/2014 Al rod, 98% RA.

To compare texture development in materials with particles to those without particles, 2014 aluminum alloy was extruded under identical conditions as the composites. To accomplish this, a 1.25 inch (31.75 mm) diameter recast ingot of 2014 aluminum was machined to the appropriate dimensions and was extruded.

Methods used to identify the changes in microstructure of the matrix, rearrangement of particles, and texture development included microscopy and x-ray diffraction. A Picker generator with four-cycle goniometer and a Siemens Crystalloflex 4 interfaced with a computer were the two x-ray systems employed to determine the texture of the matrix.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTSMicrostructure

During the plastic flow of the composite in the extrusion process, many of the SiC particles were fragmented into smaller particles (see Figure 2), and the distributions of particles were altered and changed into distributions of finer particles. The greater the RA the finer the particle distribution; Figure 3 contains the relationships of particle

Fig. 2 Breakage of an SiC particle, 40% RA.

Fig. 3 Size distribution of SiC particles.

Fig. 4 Distribution of SiC particles in aluminum matrix.

sizes for as-cast and 40%, 80% and 98% reductions of areas. Since these measurements were made at a magnification of 600x, it is likely that many fine particles, smaller than the resolution of the optical microscope used for this purpose, were not recorded. The deformation also produced some alignment of SiC particles forming stringer-like arrangements parallel to the extrusion axis, whereas, in the as-cast condition, the particles are generally random with some groups of particles attached in chain-like arrays. This effect is illustrated by the photomicrographs in Figure 4. For low deformations (less than 60% RA), particle alignment occurs in the outer region of the extruded bar, while particles in the middle region remain distributed in a pattern similar to that observed in the as-cast material. At high deformation, however, all particles in the billet appear to align in the extrusion axis.

Flow lines as revealed by sectioning and etching in 2014 aluminum are unperturbed and parallel to the extrusion axis; in the case of the composite, tortuous flow-line patterns around the hard particles are observed, as shown by Figure 5. After extensive extrusion, it was also observed that bonding between particles and matrix is improved. Although not quantitatively measured, the strengthened adherence of the particle to the matrix was apparent during metallographic surface

Fig. 5 Flow of aluminum matrix around SiC particles, extruded, 90% RA.

preparation; in the as-cast specimens most SiC particles were pulled out, but for an RA greater than 80% most of the particles remained in place.

Texture of the Matrix

In as-cast 2014 aluminum alloy and as-cast SiC/2014 aluminum, a [100] preferred crystallographic axis normal to the mold wall develops; however, the degree of the texture is lower for the as-cast SiC/2014 aluminum composite. After extrusion, a duplex fiber texture, [111] + [100], is produced in both materials. In Figure 6, pole figures for the [111] and [100] orientations of SiC/2014 aluminum after extruded 80% RA are shown; in terms of randomness, these pole figures illustrate the symmetry anticipated about the extrusion axis. If the angular deviation from the extrusion axis along any meridian to the pole of the reflecting plane is defined as ϕ , because of symmetry about the extrusion

Fig. 6 Pole figure, from computer output,
unit=random, 80% RA. (a) [111], (b) [100]

direction, the relation between pole density and ϕ are the only parameters needed to describe the preferred orientation of the extruded rods. Thus, as shown in Figure 7, plots of pole density vs ϕ for 80% RA relate to the symmetrical distribution shown by the pole figures in

Figure 6 and give satisfactory texture information for extrusion reductions.

In Figure 8 the pole densities for $\phi=0$ as function of reduction of area for the composite and the matrix aluminum alloy are compared. The [111] and [100] duplex texture develops with the increase of deformation in both materials, however, the rate of development of the [111] and [100] pole densities of the particulate composite are lower than that of the aluminum alloy. Furthermore, the [111] pole density of SiC/2014 aluminum is much lower than that of 2014 aluminum.

Fig. 7 Pole density I vs ϕ 80% RA. (a) [111], (b) [100]

Fig. 8 Pole density I ($\phi=0$)

DISCUSSION

During cross sectional reduction in the extrusion die, the metal matrix is deformed, but the hard particles are rigid and can only fragment. Consider a single, non-deformable particle that passes through the die with the matrix metal. Since the matrix is deforming in a plastic manner and the particle is not, there will be a discontinuity of flow at the interface of the particle. Experiments have shown that a separation occurs at the trailing and leading surfaces of the particle during constriction in the extrusion die [8]. For the SiC/2014 aluminum these voids are closed by the time the particle has passed through the die. By expanding on Wassermann's model [2,3] and considering plastic flow of metal around non-deformable objects, the expected general form of the flow lines is illustrated in Figure 9 and is similar to that shown by metallography in Figure 5. Thus, in the extrusion of particle composites, part of the matrix flow is perturbed locally by the particles: region 2 (boundary layer with no flow) and regions 3 and 4, where the flow lines appear at an angle to the axis because of collapsing voids -- one upstream and one downstream [8]. In region 5 the flow lines are not affected and are parallel to the extrusion axis. Because of the differences in flow direction and amount of flow, the matrix texture that develops is not as intense as with the extrusion of particle-free 2014 aluminum.

- 1 - Particle, undeformable
- 2 - Matrix, (boundary layer) undeformed, no texture
- 3 - Matrix, low deformation
- 4 - Matrix, high deformation, flow not parallel to extrusion axis
- 5 - Matrix, high deformation, flow parallel to extrusion axis

Fig. 9 Deformation model. (a) Metal (without particles),
(b) Rigid particle in MMC.

The data of McHargue, Jetter and Ogle [9] indicate that when aluminum is extruded at a high temperature, along with the deformation texture of [111], a [100] texture also appears; they conclude that the [100] is mainly caused by recrystallization occurring during hot extrusion. Herbst and Huber [10] suggest that the nucleation of recrystallized grains preferably takes place at the surface of a particle. In the experiments with SiC/2014 aluminum, extrusion deformation induced particle fracture and consequently increased the surface area, with more sites available for nucleation of recrystallized grains. Thus, there is an increase in the number of nucleation sites producing the [100] texture.

The perturbation by a particle and the arrangement of some particles in random strings in the as-cast state, lead to aligned groups of particles in the direction of major flow. As a result, these stringers permit channels of relatively uninterrupted matrix flow during the extrusion.

CONCLUSIONS

1. SiC/2014 aluminum composites develop a less intense [111] + [100] duplex fiber texture after hot extrusion than the matrix alloy which does not contain particles.
2. The inhibition of texture development of the matrix is a result of low deformation regions surrounding the hard particles and localized flow not parallel to the extrusion direction.
3. Because of extensive deformation above the recrystallization temperature, and a large number of nucleation sites, a greater proportion of the recrystallization texture is produced when particles are present.
4. The energy associated with the flow of the matrix and particles is minimized by the particles becoming aligned in the extrusion direction.

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